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I Touched the Spindle

"Attorney, good thing we bumped, may I ask some questions?" is a common phrase heard when accidentally meeting a lawyer on the street, at graduation celebrations, even at wakes, and in any instance as a free opportunity to raise legal concerns. Lawyers seem to be the problem-solvers, the superheroes, the more reliable people in the universe, and the catalysts of change. Thus, I touched the spindle.

After graduating from the University, I took and passed the qualifying exam for law school and eventually enrolled. Smirking that I finished my degree at a young age, and so I can manage taking a law degree, I touched the spindle. The 1st day was not bad at all because the professors were not around, and my classmates were from different generations and perhaps even held positions in public or private sectors. Succeeding days were spent feeding the loom; the straws were too long to roll and must be kept in an orderly manner; a long list of cases for digest, not only to read but were required to be written in a record book in the same order as they were given. I experienced sleepless nights reading and writing case digests for the following days for 3-4 subjects in a week, suffered pain in the hips due to long sitting positions, body pain, gained weight due to stress eating, and, worst of all, hypertension due to drinking too much coffee just to keep myself awake. I even excused myself from attending occasions just to read. I missed a friend's invitation to a catch-up session and drowned myself in the web of legal battles in law school. I even thought I was prepared and even lied to my classmates that I wasn't ready and hadn't read the cases beforehand, to humble myself, yet during classes, I turned out to be a moron, bathing in my own sweat. My tongue froze because the questions were beyond my comprehension and reading level. In contrast, my classmates are all busy-looking, reading their notes and books, because they might be the next person called to recite, or praying that other classmates be called, otherwise a successive doomsday.

Professors' hungers for challenge test their students' intellectual capacity by asking tricky questions that even a dog cannot answer, and if a student was able to answer, the Professor has prepared even more difficult follow-up questions that seem to have buried the student's ego to death, as his question was answered in ALAC (Answer, Legal Basis, Argument, and Conclusion) manner. Class cards serve as the class record. Once your name is called, you have to stand and assert your answer, and you cannot invoke your right to remain silent, right against discrimination, or right against data privacy, because whether you are a child of Pontius Pilate or Pontius Pilate himself, your genealogy speaks nothing; politics and the

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kompadre system will not save you. Here, there are different types of professors: the juggernaut - the supreme judge of the classroom, no other answer is correct only his, the green minded - most of the examples and jokes are related to sex, the terror - whether attend the class prepared or jump from the building for giving a wrong answer, the juris-prudence - to show off his blessed face and body, and the quality time - favorite to check attendance and dismiss the class after 15 minutes. Although the spindle of their own once touched them, weaved masterpieces from yarn of greatness using effort and consistency, which lands them their extravagant, sophisticated title of AH TEE TEE WHY.

I touched the spindle. However, I can no longer keep my composure as a human being because of those failing grades, and sooner or later, I will be kicked out of school for reaching the maximum number of failed subjects. Rather than being kicked out, I voluntarily left school and transferred to a school that accepts "flunkers," or, as they say, executioners of the humanistic approach. I touched the spindle, and it hurts no more, immune from embarrassment for not answering questions using the legal parlance, trained like a soldier standing half an hour or for the whole period depending on the Professor's discretion, religiously prayed for a 75 grade rather than failing, and if failing grades finally inked, pray harder that the same faith with classmates may adhere. Yes, what a journey it has been, a journey that tests tolerance, logical reasoning, religiosity in praying, keeping tissue in my pocket for unwanted mucus during recitation, sleeping late at night reading without understanding, and above all, a testament to pursuing a dream.

It's been a decade since the spindle in the spinning wheel stuck in my heart, the unsettled bar fight is excruciating my wellbeing, draining my resources, and keeps me haunted in a soundproof corner. Should I touch the spinning wheel and set the spindle?